

General information about the PROTEST-AIRT project

Marie Skłodowska-Curie Postdoctoral Fellowship (Grant Agreement 101057156)

Title of Project - PROTEST-AIRT – Protesting the global air transport industry: Social movements fighting for the preservation of local communities and the planet.

Principal Investigator(s): Dr Alexander ARAYA LÓPEZ, Sociologist. Faculty of Economics and Social Sciences - Section Sociology, Universität Potsdam. E-mail: [ADD EMAIL], phone number: [ADD PHONE NUMBER]

Supervisor: Dr Jürgen MACKERT, Sociologist. Faculty of Economics and Social Sciences - Section Sociology, Universität Potsdam. E-mail: [ADD EMAIL], phone number: [ADD PHONE NUMBER]

1. Purpose of the Study: The purpose of this research is to understand the contemporary global dissent against the air transport industry. The project investigates airport conflicts in Europe, with an emphasis in four cases: Berlin Brandenburg Airport in Germany, El Prat-Barcelona Airport in Spain, Bristol Airport in the United Kingdom, and Amsterdam Airport Schiphol in the Netherlands.

2. Procedures to be followed: The researcher Dr Alexander Araya López will produce several photographs during his participant observation of public protest acts of dissent against global air transport. Some of these images might focus on objects (for example, banners), but others will include protesters, both as a crowd and as individuals. You are being asked to sign a consent form allowing the publication of these photographs in various forms (including scientific publications, conferences, website, etc.), because you are clearly identifiable in some of these images. These images depicting your person will be stored in an external hard drive while being processed, and this external hard drive will be encrypted and kept at a secure location at the University of Potsdam. If you have granted your permission in the consent form, these images of your person will also be published as open data in a public repository at the end of the research, and they will be accessible to anyone. Any images of your person will be destroyed before August 31st, 2024, except for any images uploaded to an open repository (depending on your answers to this question in the respective consent form).

3. Discomforts and Risks: There are some risks associated to the publication of images of your person while participating in a political act of dissent. First, you will be clearly identifiable, and this could entail risks for your personal and professional life (for example, with your employer). Second, the published images could be used by governmental authorities (including the police) or by stakeholders from the air transport industry to track down and identify the participants in a specific protest, especially if acts of civil disobedience and other forms of radical politics were used by the protesters.

4. Benefits: The benefits to you include the opportunity to make yourself visible in your activism about the climate emergency or about the other impacts of the air transport sector in Europe and abroad. The benefits to society include the development of a series of recommendations for policymakers,

aiming both at informing entrepreneurs and the air transport representatives about the needs of the local populations and at impacting the opinion-formation and decision-taking processes at the political level (for example, in the case of local governments). This research will contribute to understand the role that air transport plays in the current global climate crisis.

5. Duration/Time: The photograph will require only a few minutes of your time.

6. Statement of Confidentiality: Your participation in this research is voluntary and your identity and personal information will be protected. The images of your person will not include your name or contact information, but you will remain identifiable.

7. Right to Ask Questions: Please contact the researcher Dr Alexander Araya López or the advisor Dr Jürgen Mackert with your questions, complaints, or concerns about this research. You can also contact them if you feel this study has harmed you. Questions about your rights as a research participant may be directed to the Ethics Committee at the University of Potsdam. For any data concerns, you can contact the Data Protection Officer, [ADD FULL NAME]: [ADD EMAIL]

8. Payment for participation: Your participation is voluntary, and you will not be compensated in any form (economic or material) because of your contribution to this research.

9. Voluntary Participation: Your decision to be in this research is voluntary. You can stop at any time. You can refuse to be photographed and you can ask the researcher to delete any images depicting your person. There will be no consequences for you if you decide to refuse your participation in this research (partially or completely). If you decide to withdraw from this study at a later phase, a statement of non-participation will be signed by the researcher, and any images of your person will be immediately destroyed.